

DELEGATION OF AUTHORITY AS A TOOL FOR MAXIMIZING ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE (A STUDY OF SELECTED MANUFACTURING FIRMS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS

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Abstract: Generally, delegation of authority has not been considered a paramount and efficient instrument in organizational administration in Nigeria as much as it is in North American and European Organizations where authority decentralization and delegation is regarded as a necessary element for effective management. Specifically, this study examined the significant effect of delegation of authority on organizational efficiency. The study also ascertained the significant impact of delegation of authority on organizational effectiveness and productivity. The study adopted descriptive and explanatory research designs. This research relied on field survey method through administering questionnaire to the respondents. The relationship between delegation and subordinate performance were examined in a field study conducted in selected manufacturing firms within Enugu metropolis. A t-test statistics was used to test the two hypotheses. The results revealed that there is a significant impact between delegation of authority and efficiency at selected manufacturing firms. This impact and factors behind it affects employee performance as well. The result also indicated that there is a significant impact between delegation of authority and effectiveness/productivity at selected manufacturing firms. This also portrays the level of influence delegation of authority has on employees individually. The study concluded that effective delegation gives subordinates the chance to incorporate their values in the work environment and, in many cases, to undertake activities of special interest to them. By increasing employees' involvement in the organization, the management boosts their enthusiasm for their work. Consequently, delegation of authority provides employees with an opportunity to invest something of themselves in their job giving them a feeling of involvement in the work as well as its results. Delegation of authority therefore enhances employee's sense of accomplishment, as it is more rewarding to be able to congratulate oneself for a task that is well planned and executed.

Keywords: Authority, Delegation, Maximizing Organizational, Performance

Introduction

Generally, in business today one of the major keys to organizational survival, growth and success largely depends on the organizations capacity to meet up with the ever increasing customer expectations. Given a proper rumination of the people-centric nature of the service industry, management employees motivation to get the best work effectiveness and continued good consumer relationship is a big dare. In every day management of the factors of production to bring about a smooth and successful operation of the business, managers and

administrators are faced with the task of properly superintending the complex nature organizational mechanism and operations.

The top level management would need to delegate tasks to the staff and this requires adequate proper flow of information, knowledge of the job and sharing of resources between the managers and the employees. Managers that delegate are more prone to have a good working relationship with their subordinates characterized by respect, mutual trust and loyalty. Consequently, employees experiencing trust and respect are likely to reciprocate by strengthening and boosting the confidence of the managers on their team (Deluga, 1994; Graen and Uhl-Bien, 1995) as quoted by (Sumi, 2004). As such, the concept of delegation can be seen as a strategic tool that builds and nourishes superior-subordinate relationships for management efficiency.

Delegation of authority is a necessary process in guaranteeing the intended organizational outcome. This is the reason behind the sharing of authority and responsibility amongst every staff considering factors like work experience, job description e.tc. which reflects the managerial development and business diversity of an organization. Also, it is hard to implement all tasks and whole business activities by employees without taking support and encouragement from high management. In this case authority delegation is considered a response for requirements of all levels to participate in decision-making to perform managerial business and division of work. One of the most pertinent points that should be taken into consideration is that administrative work focuses on defining the responsibility of an employee while using authority delegation. An employer will never avoid his responsibility to the organizational activities whether or not responsibility isn't able to be authorized or distributed to the subordinates (AL-Shrqai, 2002).

Delegation of authority is a process of assignment of tasks, transmission of authority for accomplishing the task and exaction of responsibility and obligation for the accomplishment of the task. Ile (2001) states that delegation is the assignment to another person of formal authority and accountability for carrying out specific activities. The delegation of authority by superiors to subordinates is obviously necessary for efficient functioning of any organization, since no superior can personally accomplish or completely supervise all the organization's tasks.

Although delegation is the transfer of legitimate power, it relates to the other power bases as well. When formal authority is concerned, the power to reward and punish goes with it to some extent. Expert power can also be indirectly conveyed by delegation. The subordinate who now acts in place of the superior will acquire expert power to the extent that he or she develops the necessary skills to perform the tasks. The delegation of authority is the basis of the scalar principles (Ile, 2001), the idea that a clear line of authority runs step by step from the highest to the lowest level of the organization. This clear line of authority then is the basis for all delegation. A considerable debate often arises with regard to the delegation of responsibility. A close analysis of this debate according to Kiiiza abd Picho (2014) reveals that it is more the result of semantics concerning the variables occurring in the use of language in different contexts, rather than a misunderstanding of the concept involved. Those contending that responsibility cannot be delegated support their position by stating that managers can never shed the responsibilities of their jobs by passing them on to subordinates. Those contending that responsibility can be delegated justify their position by pointing out that managers can certainly make subordinates responsible to them for certain action (Nwachukwu, 1988).

Generally, delegation of authority has not been considered a paramount and efficient instrument in organizational administration in Nigeria as much as it is in North American Organizations where authority decentralization and delegation is regarded as a necessary element for effective management, hence this study,

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the significant effect of delegation of authority on organizational efficiency.
2. To ascertain the significant impact of delegation of authority on organizational effectiveness and productivity.

2. Literature Review

Concept of Delegation of Authority

The term delegation is conceptualized by Dessler (2006) as the actions that an administrator uses to assign part of his or her authority to commensurate with the task assigned to a subordinate. Delegation of authority occurs when decision making power is assigned to a subordinate by a superior staff. This concept is further seen as authority transportation from high management to executives and to other managers.

The Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of Current English maintains that to delegate implies to appoint, entrust duties, right etc to somebody to perform a task. Ile (2001) posits that in management, delegation is the organizational process that permits the transfer of authority from a superior to a subordinate. This empowers a subordinate to make commitments, use resources and take action in relation to duties assigned to him or her.

Ile (2001) argues that no organization can function effectively without delegation whether the organization is a university, a local government unit, a profit making or non-profit making organization. The division of an organization into units or departments involves delegation. In essence delegation of authority means that a subordinate has the power to make decision and to act within explicit limits without checking with superior. Thus, when one delegate, three factors are implicit; there is assignment of responsibility, there is delegation of authority and there is a creation of accountability (Nwachukwu, 1988).

Kiiza abd Picho (2014) see delegation of authority as authorization. This involves the process of giving directives to subordinates to carry out some tasks and duties. To Lutgans and Hodgetts (2004), delegation of authority is a process of distributing responsibilities and authorities in an organization. Conceptualizing authorization, Al-Jammal *et al*, (2015); Fleith and Abd AL-Majeed, (2005) state that it is the process that involves giving responsibility to a subordinate by a manager to perform specific work for the purpose of actualizing organizational objectives. Makawi (2005) posits that authorization is granting of authority and giving the capacity to a subordinate to direct and control factors that will aid him/her perform excellently. Delegation of authority is a mechanism that builds and nourishes superior-subordinate relationships (Joiner, Bakalis and Choy, 2016).

Koontz *et al*, (1983) assert that delegation of authority involves four stages. This includes determination of result expected, the assignment of task, the delegation of authority to accomplishing these tasks, and the exaction of responsibility for their accomplishment. The scholars maintain that it is practically impossible to split this process, since expecting an employee to successfully carry out his assigned work without the authority to achieve them is a waste of time. Consequently, holding an employee responsible for the outcomes they present must be regarded as part of the baggage's that comes with delegation, hence responsibility is one of the obligations employees must live up to for the progress of the organization.

Principles of Delegation

Principles of Delegation by Results Expected: Since authority is intended to furnish managers with a tool for managing so as to gain contributions on enterprise objectives, authority delegated to an individual manager should be adequate to ensure the ability to accomplish results expected. Too many managers in the views of Al-Jammal *et al*, (2015) try to partition and define authority on the basis of the rights to be delegated or withheld, rather than looking first at the goals to be achieved and then determining how much discretion is necessary to achieve them. In no other way can a manager delegate authority in accordance with the responsibility exacted. Delegation by results expected implies that goals has been set and plans made, that these are communicated and understood, and that jobs have been set up to fit with them. It also demonstrates that planning is a prerequisite to all the tasks of management and that the managerial functions in practice come together and unite into a single activity (Ile, 2001).

Principles of Functional Definition: To develop departmentation, activities must be grouped to facilitate the accomplishment of goals, and the manager of each subdivision must have authority to coordinate its activities with the organization as a whole. This gives rise to the principles of functional definition. Joiner, Bakalis and Choy, (2016) establish that the more a position or a department has a clear definition of results expected, activities to be undertaken, organization authority delegated, and authority and informational relationships with other positions understood, the more adequately the individuals responsible can contribute towards accomplishing

enterprise objectives. To do otherwise according to Nwachukwu (1988) is to risk confusion as to what is expected of whom. This principle which is a principle of both delegation and departmentation- although simple in concept is often difficult to apply. Ile (2001) opines that to define a job and delegate authority to do it requires, in most cases patience, intelligence, and clarity of objectives and plans. It is obviously difficult to define a job if the superior does not know what results are desired.

Scalar Principle: This principle refers to the chain of direct authority relationships from superior to subordinate throughout the organization. It is obvious that organization authority must always rest somewhere. The more clear the line of authority from the top manager in an enterprise to every subordinate position, the more effective will be the responsible decision making and organization communication. Fayol (1949) describes scalar as the chain of superiors ranging from the ultimate authority to the lowest ranks. A clear understanding of the scalar principle is necessary, for the proper organization functioning. Subordinates must know who delegates authority to them and to whom matters beyond their own authority must be referred.

Authority Level Principle: This principle states that decisions within the authority competence of individuals be made by them and not be referred upward in the organization structure. In other words, managers at each level should make whatever decisions they can in the light of their delegated authority, and only matters that authority limitations keep them from deciding should be referred to superiors. The authority level principle establishes that if managers wish to make effective authority delegation and thereby to be relieved from some of the burden of decision making, they must make sure that delegations are clear and that the subordinate understands them.. Moreover, they will do well to avoid the temptation to make decisions for subordinates.

Principle of Unity of Command: A basic management principle, often disregarded for what are believed to be compelling circumstances, is that of unity of command (Fayol, 1949). The more completely an individual has a reporting relationship to a single superior, the less the problem of conflict in instructions and the greater the feeling of personal responsibility for results. In discussing delegation for authority, it has been assumed that, except for the inevitable instance of splintered authority, the right of discretion over a particular activity will flow from a single superior to a subordinate. This principle is useful in the clarification of authority- responsibility relationships.

Principle of Absoluteness of Responsibility: Since responsibility, being an obligation owed, cannot be delegated, no superior can escape, through delegation, responsibility for the activities of subordinates, for it is the superior who has delegated authority and assigned duties. Likewise, the responsibility of subordinates to their superiors for performance is absolute, once they have accepted an assignment and the right to carry it out, and superiors cannot escape responsibility for the organization for the organization activities of their subordinates.

Principle of Parity of Authority and Responsibility: Since authority is the discretionary right to carry out assignments and responsibility is the obligation to accomplish them, it logically follows that the authority should correspond to the responsibility. From this rather obvious logic is derived the principle that the responsibility for actions cannot be greater than that implied by authority delegated, nor should it be less. This parity is not mathematical, but, rather, coextensive, because both relate to the same assignments.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Democratic Leadership Theory

Democratic leadership theory supports decentralization of decision making in an organization. McGregor (1960) sees this democratic leadership theory as benevolent, participative, and believing in people. This theory is one that allows decision-making to be decentralized and shared by subordinates in order to minimize the workload on the managers. Democratic theory regards leadership as one with an underlying assumption that everyone has an equal responsibility in an outcome as well as shared contributions of expertise in decision making.

Behaviourist Theory

This theory was propounded in 1913 by John Watson. This theory takes a psychological approach which talks about scientific and objective style of investigation on what leaders actually do rather than on their qualities.

Different patterns of behaviour are studied and categorized as 'styles of leadership'. This area of study has drawn the most attention from practicing managers. Researchers were of the opinion that behaviour, unlike traits can be learned. This was interpreted that individuals trained for better leadership behaviour qualities would be able to lead more effectively. This theory is all about the study on leadership development practices.

This is because delegation is one of the practices that influence the behaviour of an employee and their performance in an organization. Mullins (2000) describes leadership styles as the way in which the manager typically behaves towards members of the group or team. Fully authority to make decisions aids and impacts on behaviour and attitude towards work and other organizational duties. Rosenbaum (1968) posits that under conditions of stress, or when great speed and efficiency are required, autocratic leadership can yield positive outcomes but If the leader is weak and incompetent, this style possesses some advantage and certain disadvantages.

EMPERICAL REVIEW

Al-Jamma et al (2015) studied the influence of the delegation of authority on employees' performance at great Irbid municipality. Staff performance were measured in relation to effectiveness, efficiency and empowerment. The data collated were analyzed via mean, standard deviation and T-test statistic. The results showed that efficiency, effectiveness as well as empowerment of employees are statistically significant to delegation of authority in Irbid municipality.

The impact of delegation on employee performance in savings and credit cooperative societies in Kisii County, Kenya was studied by Kombo, et al, (2014). T-test statistics, mean and percentage were adopted to analyze the collected data. The result indicated that effective delegation of authority in organization has a direct positive relationship with staff performance and organizational performance in general.

Joiner, et al. (2016) conducted a research on delegation, job satisfaction and subordinate performance: The mediating effect of leader-member exchange. They used a survey research design where 260 questionnaires were shared to the Chinese subordinates working in Hong Kong transport company. The path analysis of the regression results indicated that delegation of authority has a positive relationship with leader-member exchange (LMX) relationship.

The research done by Shekari, Naieh, & Nouri (2011) studied the relationship between authority delegation process and rate of effectiveness: case study municipality regions of Mashhad. Delegation of authority in this case measured by preparation, appreciation stage and effective-ness. Correlation analysis was adopted as a way of analyzing the collected data. The outcomes of this study indicated that there is a remarkable relationship between the level of effectiveness and authority delegation process.it is also noteworthy to recognize that appreciation and preparation stages have the most influence on effectiveness.

Kiiza & Picho (2014) conducted an empirical investigation on delegation and employee commitment in the School of Finance and Banking in Kigali, Rwanda: A cross-sectional survey design was adopted with sample size of 97. Carefully selected and random sampling were employee as sampling techniques. The findings indicated that staff commitment is positively correlated with delegation of authority.

The study of Shekari et al (2011) on the relationship between delegation of authority process and rate of effectiveness. The result of this study indicated that in general, between the delegation authority process and rate of effectiveness, there was a momentous correlation. The study equally indicated that stages involved in delegation authority such as preparation, appreciation stage and effectiveness had a noteworthy positive relationship.

Fehr et al (2011) did a study on the lure of authority: motivation, Authority and power. This study experimentally investigated the motivation and incentive effect of authority in an authority-delegation game. Employees often retain authority even when its delegation is in their material interest suggesting that authority appears to be valued by the individual even above a potential monetary gain if this authority was delegated. The study showed that

authority also leads to excessive show of effort by controlling staff, while a good percentage indicated less effort despite incentives to the contrary.

The study of Darwish (2010) did a study on the delegation of authority as the best method to raise the efficiency of job performance. This study aims to diagnose the actual reality of the exercise of the authority delegated by the organization and its impact on the performance efficiency. viewing the concept of delegation of authority as an act of administrative and positive role functionality in the efficiency of work in an organization.

AL-Matouh (2003) studied the role of delegation of authority in achieving the objectives of organizing. The research found that delegation of authority played a vital role in running a successful business. It raises the morale among workers and allows the chance for staff building which enables these employees to practice a form of alternative leadership and ability to manage businesses.

Wadi (2009) conducted study on the impact of authority delegation on managerial performance. The research aimed at identifying the effect of authority delegation on workers performance of Sudan University of Science & Technology (SUST). Sample of the study was made up of 60 workers and they were randomly selected. The study realized the following results: delegation of authority strengthens human relations among members of the organization, enhance self-confidence among workers and increase the level of achievement in duties and work assigned for workers and speed of implementation the assigned duties respectively.

AL-joqi (2010) researched on the impact of delegation of authority on the effectiveness of management decisions. The results realized from this research have shown that the level of applying authority delegation in yamen Oil Company was low. Also, it is evident that there is a strong and positive relation between successes of delegation process and departmental success.

Senyuta (2013) carried out a study on delegation and performance. This paper empirically studied how the level of authority delegation is related to the performance of an organization. The study revealed that Decentralized, horizontal organizational structure is prone to more efficient decision making. Such decentralization often results the loss of control and the need to give a form of incentives to the employees or managers that are legitimately given the authority to make decisions. This is a possibility that an organization considers when deciding on the level of authority delegation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study used descriptive and explanatory research designs. The descriptive design was adopted because, according to Kothari,(2003), descriptive design is a method of securing information concerning an existing phenomenon from all or a selected number of respondents of the concerned organization or community. Explanatory design was adopted because the research aimed at collecting information from employees on their unbiased take and opinions in relation to the effects of delegation on employee performance.

This research relied on field survey method through administering questionnaire to the respondents. The relationship between delegation and subordinate performance were examined in a field study conducted in selected manufacturing firms within Enugu metropolis. Participants were employees of the company who had upward and downward lines of reporting. The selected manufacturing firms were selected as the focus of this study because of their significant contribution to the economy of Enugu state and Nigeria in general.

Simple random sampling technique was employed to administer the highly structured questionnaires. A 4-point Likert Scale was used to rank the respondents responses. A total of 150 questionnaires were administered to the respondents but only 100 were returned and found viable and data were analyzed via descriptive and explanatory statistics. The reliability of the responses obtained was tested via Cronbach Alpha to check the internal consistency of the data.

A Questionnaire was the main instrument of data collection. A questionnaire that is made up of both closed-ended and open- ended questions which were written in accordance with the objectives of the study and was administered to the selected sample. The questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection because it is facile and economical to administer in terms of time and money. It is also prone to greater number of response.

The data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses was tested using t-test statistical instrument.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1: IMPACT OF DELEGATION IN THE ORGANIZATIONAL EFFICIENCY

	SD	D	N	A	SA	total	mean	STD.DEV
Delegation is used in the company frequently	2	9	10	51	28	100	3.94	3.535533906
Delegated tasks save time and resources	2	20	10	47	21	100	3.65	3.292415527
My immediate superior follow-up on the delegated tasks that I undertake.	2	6	17	52	23	100	3.88	3.46121366
I receive a reward or recognition on all successful delegated tasks that I undertake.	5	9	18	44	24	100	3.73	3.367491648
I mostly delegable tasks that the subordinate is an expert in	1	20	21	41	17	100	3.53	3.1591138
More than 50% of my daily work are delegated	10	15	26	31	18	100	3.32	3.029851482
I delegate 50% of my daily work to others	13	25	30	25	7	100	2.88	2.588435821
Majority of the tasks I delegate or are delegated to me are successful	7	6	13	53	21	100	3.75	3.385262176
	42	110	145	344	159		28.68	25.81931802
SCORES	AVERAGE	5.25	13.75	18.125	43	19.875	3.585	3.227414752

Source: field survey 2021

In this study, investigations to find out from the respondents whether official tasks were delegated in the company revealed from the data presented in the Table above that majority of the respondents (79%) agreed that delegation was employed in the institution frequently. In extension, 68% of the respondents agreed that delegated tasks save

time and resources. Majority of the respondents (75%) agreed that their immediate boss/ superior followed up on the delegated tasks that are assigned to them. It is also notable that 68% of the respondents agreed that they received recognition on all successful delegated tasks that they took on. A good number of the respondents (41.4%) agreed that they intermittently select the tasks they believe the subordinates are experts in to delegate. It was also observed that many of the respondents (49%) agreed that more than 50% of their daily jobs are delegated while 38.0% of the respondents disagreed that they delegate 50% of their daily tasks to their subordinates. In conclusion, a large number of the respondents (74%) agreed that those that most of the task they delegate to others or the one's delegated to them were successfully completed.

Delegation upgrades the level of job performance	3	8	15	46	28	100	3.88	3.489986
Delegation creates the spirit of entrepreneurship in employees	5	25	8	45	17	100	3.44	3.127299
Delegation accelerates decision making process	6	10	14	49	21	100	3.69	3.334666
Delegation raises amount of work accomplished	9	14	15	40	22	100	3.52	3.221801
Delegation improves perception between employer and employee	8	25	12	39	16	100	3.3	3.016621
Delegation ensures work continues in managers absence	16	13	21	31	19	100	3.24	3.006659
Delegation helps me carry out my task in little time	10	21	23	29	17	100	3.22	2.946184
Delegation gives avenue for more work to be done	8	12	11	51	18	100	3.59	3.258834
	42	128	119	330	158		27.88	25.40205
	5.25	16	14.875	41.25	19.75		3.485	3.175256

TABLE 2: IMPACT OF DELEGATION OF AUTHORITY ON ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS AND PRODUCTIVITY

SOURCE: Field Study 2021

In this study, investigations to find out from the respondents whether delegation upgrades the level of performance in the company revealed from the data presented in the Table above that majority of the respondents (74%) agreed that delegation was a catalyst to high performance in the institution. In extension, 62% of the respondents agreed

that delegated tasks help to create the spirit of entrepreneurship in the employees. Majority of the respondents (70%) agreed that delegation of authority accelerates decision making process. It is also notable that 62% of the respondents agreed that delegation increases the amount of work accomplished. A good number of the respondents (55%) agreed that delegation of tasks helps to improve perceptions between employer and employee. It was also observed that many of the respondents (50%) agreed that work at the office continues without the manager in charge present while 46.0% of the respondents agreed that delegation of authority helps them carry out their job in less time. In conclusion, a considerable number of the respondents (69%) agreed that delegation of authority gives an avenue for more work to be done.

STATEMENT OF HYPOTHESES

H1: delegation of authority has no significant impact on organizational efficiency

Solution:

$$t = \frac{\sum d}{\sqrt{\frac{n(\sum d^2) - (\sum d)^2}{n-1}}}$$

where d: difference per paired value

n: number of samples

H0: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ the paired t test formula was applied:

H1: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$

Table 3: PAIRED T TEST

A/SA		D/SD	
Agree+ strongly agree		Disagree + strongly disagree	
79		11	
68		22	
75		8	
68		14	
58		21	
49		25	
32		38	
74		13	
			t test paired
mean	62.875	mean	19 0.001707

From the table above, the t calculated is 0.001707. from the tabulation and computation it is evident that the mean value and consistency of A/SA is greater than D/SD. With t test value of 0.001707 which meets to 5% significance level we reject the alternative hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a significant impact between delegation of authority and efficiency at selected manufacturing firms. This impact and factors behind it affects employee performance as well.

H1 delegation of authority has no significant impact on organizational effectiveness and productivity

Table 4: paired t test

Agree/strongly agree	Disagree/strongly disagree
74	11
63	30
70	16
62	23
55	33
50	29
46	31
69	20
61.125	24.125
t test (paired)	0.000516

From the table above, the t calculated is 0.000516. from the tabulation and computation, it is evident that the mean value and consistency of A/SA is greater than D/SD. With t test value of 0.000516 which meets to 5% significance level we reject the alternative hypothesis. We therefore conclude that there is a significant impact between delegation of authority and effectiveness/productivity at selected manufacturing firms. This also portrays the level of influence delegation of authority has on employees individually.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The increase in globalization brought about numerous changes in organizations and businesses globally. These changes are due to the result of international competitive pressure faced by enterprises operating in a knowledge driven productive economy (Wokoma and Iheriohanma, 2010). Predominant number of employees agreed that their tasks are decided by their Supervisors/ Managers. These respondents agreed that there was delegation of tasks and responsibilities but consultations were also necessary. The study also established that, delegation saved time and organizational resources. Consequently, delegation enabled employees to be creative and innovative while rewarding them with motivational incentives. When the majority of organizational plans and objectives are accomplished through the use of management instruments like delegation, it gives the organization a competitive edge over others that do not delegate.

This made it paramount to carefully consider and adopt favorable management practices that will ensure management efficiency and overall success. Thus, prompting the research, the collated Data was analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively in other to give more information on the negating and supporting factors pertaining to delegation. The research was done through the data obtained in the questionnaires and its analysis. The aim was to apply data collection and analytics within the context of management in order to generate ideas,

instead of wise guesses and assumptions. In a nutshell this study was focused on the how delegation can be used to increase employee performance and ultimately organizational efficiency.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Delegation involves distribution of new responsibilities and authority to employees. Organizations employing delegation as a management instrument leads to increased human capability and sustainable competitive advantage. Findings in this research shows that majority of the respondents agreed that delegation was used in the institution frequently, that the superior staff followed up on the delegated tasks that they undertook, that they were given tasks they were experts in, that delegation of work saves enormous time and resources and that they received reward or recognition on all successful delegated tasks undertaken. Results of the Likert 5-scale analysis indicated that delegation statistically and positively impacted the organizational performance of. The mean and standard deviation of this model showed an average mean of 3.585 and 3.2 respectively. This implies that majority of the respondents agree mostly that delegation has been tested at the company and it has contributed to organizational efficiency in addition to realization of set goals/objectives. The adoption of delegation of authority as a tool for management efficiency had a significant influence on the performance of selected manufacturing firms, this is evident in various responses and verbal testimonies of the employees. This study equally highlighted that delegation of authority helps in improvement of skills and competences of employees which leads to improved performance. It is therefore noteworthy that delegation is a very important factor in enhancing efficiency in management and overall performance of any organization.

Finally, the results in this study concurred to (Axley 1992) as cited by Eddie (2002) that effective delegation gives subordinates the chance to incorporate their values in the work environment and, in many cases, to undertake activities of special interest to them. By increasing employees' involvement in the organization, the management boosts their enthusiasm for their work. Consequently, delegation of authority provides employees with an opportunity to invest something of themselves in their job giving them a feeling of involvement in the work as well as its results. Delegation of authority therefore enhances employee's sense of accomplishment, as it is more rewarding to be able to congratulate oneself for a task that is well planned and executed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The study recommends business organizations to progress the process of activating managerial authority delegation for employees and increasing the level of delegation confirms with the amount of tasks in order to upgrade job performance.
2. The necessity for studying the mechanism and improving managerial efficiency and using delegation to influence employees' satisfaction level in all fields.

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